

Review of existing methods for assessing walking ability in broiler chickens

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Introduction

Walking ability is a highly important animal-based indicator of welfare in broilers. Impaired walking ability can hinder birds' capability to access resources such as food and water, prevent them from performing motivated behaviours, are linked with increased morbidity and mortality rates and may be associated with pain (McGeown et al., 1999; Danbury et al., 2000; Bradshaw et al., 2002; Granquist et al., 2019; Riber et al., 2021). Currently, multiple methods exist to assess walking ability that vary in the level of observer training required, the equipment required and the overall feasibility of implementation. Currently, gait scoring remains the most widely used method due to its ease of being implemented on-farm, however its subjectivity can make comparison between farms scored by different observers difficult. This has led to the development of more objective assessment methods such as obstacle courses, the latency to lie test, the rotarod test, kinetic and kinematic approaches as well as the assessment of activity levels. Computer vision has potential for collecting data automatically and non-invasively, however these techniques need further development and refinement before they can serve as a replacement for traditional gait scoring. The latency to lie test appears to be highly linked with gait scores and could serve as an objective alternative to gait scoring, however more validation of this test is required. A method for assessing walking ability needs to be both valid and feasible for use on commercial farms and to compare between facilities inspected by different observers. It also needs to be able to be conducted in a reasonable amount of time. Therefore, the aim of this review is to examine the technical and scientific literature on existing methods for assessing walking ability in broilers, as well as to assess the reliability, validity, and feasibility of the different methods, when available.

Methods

A literature search was conducted in September 2023 using the Web of Science database. Search terms consisted of the following combinations: walking + ability + method + broiler; gait + score + broiler; latency + to + lie + broiler; obstacle + test + broiler; runway + broiler. The obtained literature was also screened for relevant references using the snowball method. Literature was evaluated regardless of the publication year. Technical documents, such as those from animal welfare audit organizations were obtained using Google. Only methods for assessment of broilers were included and post-mortem assessment methods were excluded. For each publication, information regarding the methodology, feasibility for on-farm use, and any reliability or validity statistics were collected.

Results

Gait scoring

Available methods

Gait scoring is currently the most extensively used method for assessing broiler walking ability on-farm. Kestin and colleagues (1992) developed a 6-point ordinal scale for the visual assessment of walking ability which ranges from a score of 0 where the bird walks with no detectable abnormality, up to a score of 5 where the bird is unable to maintain a walk on its feet and locomotion can only be achieved with the assistance of the wings or by crawling on

the shanks (Table A1). This system is commonly referred to as the Bristol scale and is often used as the gold standard for assessing walking ability, for the validation of novel or alternative scoring methods, and in animal welfare assurance schemes such as the Global Animal Partnership (GLOBAL G.A.P., 2013). Previous methods for assessing leg health involved identifying specific skeletal abnormalities, however, their link with walking ability is not always strong. For instance, walking ability may be impaired by muscular or neurological conditions which may not be easily detected. Therefore, Kestin et al. (1992) aimed to develop a method which allows for the direct assessment of a bird's ability to walk.

Scoring with the Bristol scale is to be conducted by two observers simultaneously, with one observing from above as they gently encourage a bird to walk, and another observing from the side in a crouched position. Once a consensus between the observers is reached, the score is documented. However, in practice, scoring is commonly conducted by just one observer. To assess a flock, a sample of birds are individually scored from multiple locations within the house (and possibly on the range if there is one present). Depending on the conditions, a pen may be utilized to corral groups of birds, such as with low stocking densities. Otherwise, birds may be assessed freely in the barn, such as when birds are too flighty to be corralled. Gait scoring using this method is relatively quick, with the assessment of 100 birds per hour being possible (Kestin et al., 1992). In the study by Kestin et al. (1992), 300 broilers were assessed by the same two observers at two timepoints within the same day. Of these broilers, 55% received the same score at both timepoints, while 24% received higher scores and 21% received lower scores than at the previous assessment. A Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed ranks test showed no significant difference between the two sets of scores. A moderate Spearman's rank correlation of 0.72 was reported, however reliability values above 0.80 are considered acceptable in behavioural research (Bateson and Martin, 2021).

The Welfare Quality® Assessment Protocol for poultry includes a gait scoring method for broilers which is very similar to the Bristol scale (Welfare Quality®, 2009). The protocol states that scoring should be conducted as close to slaughter age as possible. This method suggests using catch pens in random locations throughout the house to score approximately 150 birds. Each bird should be encouraged to walk out of the pen, one at a time. A flock average score is then calculated. Scoring is done on a 6-point scale, where 0 represents birds that are normal, dexterous, and agile, and 5 represents birds that are incapable of walking (Table A2). Similarly, the RSPCA Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol uses a 6-point scale to score birds after being observed walking for at least 10 paces (RSPCA, 2017). These range from 0, where the bird displays smooth, fluid locomotion, to 5, where the bird is incapable of sustained walking on its feet (Table A3).

Gait scoring is inherently subjective and requires training and practice on live animals with experienced observers present. Results of an assessment have been shown to be impacted by the background and experience of the person performing the scoring, making it challenging to make direct comparisons between flocks scored by different observers (Butterworth et al., 2007). While proper training can improve scoring accuracy (Butterworth et al., 2007), the subjectivity of this method remains a topic of discussion and modified techniques have been introduced (Garner et al., 2002; Dawkins et al., 2004; Webster et al., 2008; Yalçın et al., 2010).

In an effort to increase the objectivity of gait scoring, Garner et al. (2002) modified the Bristol scale through the addition of more objective inclusion/exclusion criteria for each category and standardized the method of observation (Table A4). Similar to Kestin et al. (1992), birds were captured in groups into a small pen, with one observer scoring from above within the pen, and a second scoring at bird level outside the pen. The observer inside the pen would always approach individual birds from behind, as angled approaches from the side can alter locomotor behaviour in ways that may be mistaken as limping. Gait scores of 0 and 5 remained essentially the same as described in Kestin et al. (1992). If a sitting bird did not rise within 5 s after being approached or handled, then it could be scored either a 4 or a 5, with those scored a 4 being able to take at least one step after being picked up and placed in a standing position. Birds that did rise within 5 s of being approached would be scored either a 0, 1, 2, or 3. These individuals would be picked up and placed in a standing position. Those that sat within 15 s or less were given a score of 3. Those that stayed standing for longer than 15 s were further assessed. Those with an identifiable leg issue (e.g., a limp) were given a score of 2. Those with a slightly unsteady gait or the absence of furling of the feet when raised were given a score of 1. Humane Farm Animal Care recommends the use of this modified scoring system in on-farm inspections for their Certified Humane® label (Humane Farm Animal Care).

The reliability of this method was assessed by recruiting a group of observers with no prior experience assessing walking ability in broilers. In total, 18 observers including undergraduate students, graduate students and postdoctoral researchers participated. Half of the observers were trained on the Bristol scale and half on the modified system. 18 birds (3 from each score) that received the same score from both observers during live observations were also video recorded at a side angle for a reliability assessment. Test-retest values by the same observer were higher than reported by Kestin et al. (1992) with reliabilities of 0.906 when using the Bristol scale and 0.948 when using the modified scale, even with unexperienced observers. The inter-rater reliability using the Bristol scale was 0.892 and was 0.943 when using the modified scale. The authors did not find significant differences in the difficulty or time required to use either scoring system. When comparing scores between the inexperienced and experienced observers, the most disagreement was found for birds with a gait score of 2, with inexperienced observers tending to give the birds a lower score. In this study, reliability for the Bristol scale was acceptable (i.e., greater than 0.8), though the modified score showed significantly improved reliability values. The higher values reported here than in Kestin et al. (1992) could be explained by the fact that birds with ambiguous scores were excluded from the video observations used to calculate reliabilities in Garner et al. (2002). In practice, it could be expected that the reliability of the method would be lower as scoring would take place on farm without the ability to strictly control viewing angles, replay videos or exclude individuals with ambiguous gaits.

Other groups have aimed to further simplify the Bristol gait score by reducing it down to a three- (Dawkins et al., 2004; Webster et al., 2008) or four-point scale (Yalcin et al., 1998). For instance, Dawkins et al. 2004 utilized a three-point scoring system where a score of 0 was assigned to birds that walked with ease, had regular and even strides and were well balanced, a score of 1 to birds that walked with irregular and uneven strides and appeared unbalanced and a score of 2 to birds that were reluctant to move and were unable to walk many strides

before sitting down (Table A5). A single bird from 10 locations within a house was observed walking for at least 10 paces before assigning them a score. Details regarding the number or experience of observers, whether birds were encouraged to walk, and the angle that birds were viewed from were not reported in the study. No validation of the test was performed.

Webster et al. (2008) aimed to validate a three-point scoring system (termed the “U.S. Gait Scoring System”) which was developed by the National Chicken Council for use in welfare audits within the United States (National Chicken Council, 2022). The scoring system was developed to improve the ability to compare between flocks audited by different individuals. The scores were defined as follows: score 0 = no impairment, bird can walk at least 5 ft with a balanced gait, bird may appear ungainly but with little effect on function, score 1 = obvious impairment, birds can walk at least 5 ft but with a clear limp or decidedly awkward gait, and score 2 = severe impairment, bird will not walk 5 ft, may shuffle on shanks or hocks with assistance of wings (Table A6). This scoring system allows for the distinction between birds with no impairments (score of 0) versus those with walking impairments (scores of 1 and 2). The decision to utilize a three-point scale, as opposed to a binary (impaired/not impaired) was to allow the auditor to assess the producer’s culling program, as those with a score of 2 have severely compromised welfare and should be culled. A total of 681 broilers were scored simultaneously using both the three-point scale (two observers) and the Bristol scale (2 additional observers). The observers were a mix of poultry science professors, technicians, graduate and undergraduate students that were familiar with broiler chickens but had never performed gait scoring. The observers were provided with written descriptions of the scoring systems and worked with an experienced scorer on live birds until they were proficient. Scoring was performed from outside a test pen as a handler encouraged birds to walk in an open area towards other birds. Two trials were conducted, one on the university farm, and one across ten commercial farms. If needed, the encouragement consisted of approaching the birds from behind, tapping the test pen near the birds, or gently prodding the bird with plastic tubing or a foot.

Within-observer agreement (test-retest) was assessed by having the observers score the same birds again the following day. Weighted kappa values indicated strong within-observer agreement, with similar values reported for the three-point (0.67) and Bristol scoring systems (0.68). Significant positive associations between the first and second scores for both scoring systems were also shown through Spearman rank correlations (three point = 0.68, Bristol = 0.69). Similar within-observer agreements were found for the Bristol scale as reported by Kestin et al. (1992). These values were lower than those reported by Garner et al. (2002) which could be expected as these scores were performed on live birds under farm-conditions, whereas Garner used video recordings of birds with unambiguous gaits. Between-observer agreements were high for both the three-point (0.63) and Bristol (0.72) scoring systems as indicated by the kappa values obtained during the trial conducted on the university farm, though they were slightly higher for the Bristol scale. Spearman rank correlations were in agreement with the kappa values (three-point = 0.62, Bristol = 0.71). During the second trial conducted on commercial farms, the kappa values were 0.78 and 0.65 and the Spearman correlations were 0.84 and 0.74 for the three-point and Bristol systems, respectively. The

Spearman correlation values were lower in this study conducted under farm conditions ($r = 0.74$) than those reported in Garner et al. (2002) ($r = 0.89$) under highly controlled conditions.

Yalcin et al. (1998) gait scored broilers using a four-point scale as follows: 0 = the bird walked normally with no detectable abnormality, 1 = the bird was able to walk but had an obvious gait defect, 2 = the bird had a severe gait defect and walked only when driven, 3 = the bird did not walk (Table A7). The scoring was conducted simultaneously by two observers with different viewpoints of the birds. Birds were reassessed if an agreement was not reached between the observers. The reliability of this scoring system was not reported.

Impacts of sampling method

Even when using the same scoring scale, differences in methodology such as using a pen, number and position of the observers, number of birds scored or whether or not birds are encouraged to walk can potentially bias outcomes (Garner et al., 2002; Cordeiro et al., 2009; Almeida Paz et al., 2019). Various sampling methods have been recommended when performing gait scoring. For instance, Grandin (2020) recommended sampling a total of 100 broilers between 2 locations within the house when conducting on-farm welfare audits, whereas Dawkins et al. (2004) suggested scoring a single bird randomly selected from 10 locations within the house (for a total of 10 birds scored per house).

Cordeiro et al. (2009) compared three sampling methods: 1) 100 birds were randomly selected, enclosed in a circle, stimulated to walk out of the circle, half of the birds were scored; 2) Ten birds were selected randomly and gait scored; 3) 100 birds were randomly selected, enclosed in a circle, and observed while walking away from the circle without being stimulated to walk, half of the birds were scored. Gait scoring was conducted using the three-point system described in Dawkins et al. (2004) by a single experienced observer. The authors concluded that method 2 (scoring 10 randomly selected birds within the house) appeared to be the least reliable method of sampling, as evidenced by the high standard error around the mean. The distribution of gait scores obtained using method 2 showed a different pattern than those for methods 1 and 3, suggesting that this method likely overestimated the number of birds with gait scores of 0 and 3, and underestimated the number of birds with gait scores of 2. When birds were stimulated to walk (method 1), the average gait score was lower than when they were not stimulated to walk (method 3). At 28 days of age, when using method 1, 2% of birds received a score of 2, whereas 20% received this score when using method 3. This could be attributed to the belief that broilers may ignore some degree of pain when exposed to novel or fear inducing stimuli, which could lead to them mistakenly being assigned a lower gait score than they would receive if observed walking undisturbed (Webster et al., 2008; Almeida Paz et al., 2019).

Almeida Paz et al. (2019) found evidence that birds may suppress discomfort when stimulated to walk, which could bias gait scoring results. The study aimed to examine the walking speed of broilers with various gait scores with and without the use of a stimulus. Gait scoring was conducted using a three-point scale, where 0 = healthy birds that exhibited no abnormality when walking, 1 = birds that exhibited difficulty to walk that impacted their locomotion ability in a way that was easily identifiable through observation and 2 = birds that exhibited severe issues and walked only when highly motivated. 970 birds in total were gait scored, then a

subset of birds with clear scores were selected for assessment of walking speed (46 with gait score 0, 23 with gait score 1, and 5 with gait score 2). The birds were video recorded walking across a 1m long test platform that was covered in 8 cm of wood shavings with and without a sound stimulus. The sound stimulus used was clapping hands, which reached levels between 60 and 80 dB. Speed in cm/s was calculated from the videos. Walking speed was significantly associated with gait score, with birds with a gait score of 0 walking the fastest and those with a gait score of 2 walking the slowest. With all gait score categories, birds walked significantly faster when receiving the sound stimulus compared to when no stimulus was used.

Summary

Gait scoring using the 6-point Bristol scale remains the most extensively utilized system in experimental studies, assessment schemes, and in the validation of novel walking ability assessment methods. The largest weakness of this method is its subjective nature which sometimes leads to low observer reliability (Butterworth et al., 2007). To ensure high reliability, fairly extensive training of observers is required, and training with live birds and with an experienced observer present is highly recommended (Webster et al., 2008). During assessments, it is recommended that birds are assessed by two observers simultaneously, one from above and one from the side (Martrenchar et al., 1999; Webster et al., 2008), which is often not feasible due to limited personnel resources or biosecurity restrictions. Methodology should be carefully considered with regard to how they may bias outcomes. For instance, encouraging the birds to walk may result in lower (better) gait scores as even birds with poor gait scores can walk relatively well under pressure. For this reason, some systems advise against encouraging birds to walk (Webster et al., 2008). An additional pitfall to gait scoring is that the method itself may invoke fear or pain, especially if birds with injuries are forced to stand and walk.

Obstacle courses and runways

In response to concerns regarding the reliability of the gait scoring methods, two validated, objective behavioural tests have been developed. These involve measuring the duration of time required for a bird to cross a runway or an obstacle course, and measuring the duration of time that they can remain standing (see “Latency to lie” section).

Individual obstacle tests

An obstacle test involves placing a bird at one end of a test corridor with a motivating factor such as food or conspecifics at the opposite end. Obstacles, such as hurdles, are placed along the corridor that birds must navigate to reach the other side. The time it takes the bird to walk from the start position to an end position is recorded, with the idea being that birds with reduced walking abilities will take longer to complete the task. The number of obstacle crossings is sometimes also recorded.

This test has been used in multiple studies to explore the impact of administering NSAIDs to birds. For instance, McGeown et al. (1999) utilized an obstacle course test to assess the impact of administering NSAIDs to birds classified as either lame or not lame (a score of 0 or 3 on the Bristol scale, respectively). The time that birds took to navigate two hurdles (15 and 20 cm high) and reach the end with food and conspecifics was recorded. In this study, the birds with gait scores of 3 took significantly longer to complete the course, suggesting they either had

poorer walking ability and/or were less motivated to seek food and social interaction. Birds that received the NSAID treatment completed the course significantly faster than those that did not, suggesting that the treatment improved the birds' ability to walk, likely through the reduction of inflammation and perception of pain.

In another study assessing the impact of an NSAID on pain and Bristol gait score, researchers employed a runway test (Tahamtani et al., 2021). Birds were placed at one end of a 311 cm long runway with feed, mealworms, and conspecifics at the other end. Three zones were marked along the length of the corridor, each measuring 67 cm. Two test sessions were performed and video recorded. In the first, no obstacles were included, and in the second, two wooden obstacles (with heights of 16 and 18 cm, respectively) were placed across the runway. The latency to leave the start box and to reach the end of the corridor were noted, as well as the number and time point of each crossing into a new zone. Birds were allowed a maximum of 180 s to complete the course. Birds with a gait score of 0 were significantly faster to reach the end of the runway with obstacles than birds with a gait score of 2 and tended to be faster than birds with a gait score of 1. In the test without obstacles, no relationship between gait score and behaviour in the runway was found.

Another study aimed at assessing analgesic effects tested birds using a 2 m long runway (Singh et al., 2017). Individual birds were classified as either lame (Bristol gait scores of 3 and 4) or non-lame (gait scores from 0 to 2). The arena had a 15 cm tall wooden barrier across the centre, and food and a conspecific were placed at the far end as a reward. Time to finish the course was recorded in s. In all tests, the non-lame groups of birds completed the course faster than the lame groups.

Bokkers and Koene (2002) employed a runway test to gain insight into motivation in relation to physical ability in broilers with various gait scores (obtained using the Bristol method). A 2 m long runway with 5 bowls placed along its length was used in testing. Individual birds participated in three sessions, a control (mealworms were provided in bowls along the runway), a frustration (all but the last bowls were empty) or obstacle session (mealworms were provided along runway and four wooden obstacles that were 10 cm high and 5 cm wide were placed along the runway). It was observed that some birds required resting time during the sessions and would sit down, either on the floor or on top of the obstacles, however no significant correlations were found between walking speed, body weight and gait score.

Group obstacle tests

As obstacle tests on individual birds can be time consuming to perform, researchers have adapted the test for use on groups of birds. A Group Obstacle test developed by Caplen et al. (2014) has been used to explore the effects of various pharmaceutical treatments for pain relief (Caplen et al., 2014; Hothersall et al., 2016). Groups of individually marked lame (gait scores of 3 to 4 on the Bristol scale) and non-lame (gait scores of 0 and 1) birds were housed in pens containing a drinker and a feeder separated by a 10 cm tall block barrier. Continuous video recordings were taken over a 5 h period. The number of “crossings” (each time a bird stepped up onto the obstacle) and the latency of each bird’s first crossing attempt were recorded. In Caplen et al. (2014), non-lame broilers made a significantly greater number of obstacle crossings than the lame broilers, suggesting that the test may provide a good

indication of leg health. As eating and drinking are socially facilitated behaviours, the authors suggested that testing birds in groups could be beneficial to help motivate all birds to attempt to cross the obstacle. Without any motivation it may have been more difficult to assess the birds' physical ability. In Hothersall et al. (2016) where a similar test was conducted, gait score was found to be a significant factor in their models examining latency to cross and number of obstacle crossings, however they did not find associations between drug treatment and activity within the test.

Santos et al. (2022) aimed to assess the walking ability of various broiler genotypes with different growth rate classifications using a group obstacle test. A subset of birds (6 in total) from each pen were individually marked. Feed was withdrawn for 1 hour prior to the test. For testing, birds were corralled to the end with the water line and an obstacle was placed across the centre of the pen. A feeder was available at the opposite side of the pen. The birds were video recorded for 5 hours and the latency to first cross the obstacle and the total number of crossings (completely going over the obstacle) were recorded. This test was conducted at two target weights, 2.1 kg and 3.2 kg. At the target weight of 2.1 kg, the slow growing birds had the greatest number of crossings, while no differences were observed between the other growth rate categories. The slow-growing birds had a tendency to have a shorter latency to cross the obstacle than the conventional broilers. At the target weight of 3.2, the slow-growing genotypes had a greater number of crossings than the fast-growing and conventional birds, while the moderate-growing birds were not significantly different from the other categories. At this target weight there were no significant differences in latency to first cross the obstacle between the different growth rate categories.

Summary

Birds with lower gait scores have been shown to complete the obstacle course quicker and to perform a greater number of obstacle crossings, however this relationship is not always significant when tested experimentally. It is possible that a bird's motivation to reach the other side can impact the results of the test. For instance, a bird with a gait score of 0 may remain in the start area of the test due to fear or lack of motivation to reach the other side, leading to a very long duration which would incorrectly be interpreted as poor walking ability. Obstacle tests also require a habituation period and can be quite time consuming if all birds are tested individually. Use of video recording equipment can further add to time, labour and equipment costs. Biosecurity restrictions may prevent necessary equipment from being transferred between farms. These barriers mean that while these tests hold value in experimental settings, they are likely not practical for use on commercial farms.

Latency to lie

The latency to lie (LTL) test is another validated and objective behavioural test for the assessment of walking ability. This test consists of measuring the duration that birds can remain standing, with longer durations being associated with better walking ability. There are a few variations of this test including the use or absence of water (an aversive stimulus), whether birds are tested individually or in a group, or whether they are tested in a container or without restriction in the house.

Latency to lie with water

Weeks et al. 2002 were the first to develop the latency lie test as an objective method for assessing leg health. The test consists of measuring the length of time that birds remain standing in shallow water – a novel stimulus, believed to be aversive, that would encourage birds to remain standing as long as possible. Sitting or lying are postures that remove weight from the birds' limbs, providing them with relief if they experience pain or discomfort from conditions relating to their legs. It is presumed that birds with good leg health would be able to remain standing for a longer time than those with leg impairments. In this study, individually marked broilers with known gait scores (Bristol scale) were placed in groups of 16 into a test pen that could hold water. After a brief habituation period, tepid water (32°C) to a depth of 3 cm was added, prompting all birds to stand. A stopwatch was then started and the latency until each bird lied down was recorded. Birds were removed from the test pen after they lied down. A significant effect of gait score on latency to lie down was found, with birds having higher gait scores remaining standing for much shorter periods.

Berg and Sanotra (2003) modified the LTL test developed by Weeks et al. (2002) with the intent of making it easier to use in commercial broiler houses. Modifications included testing the birds individually without visual contact with other birds and using an already filled tub of water (3 cm depth at 32°C) in which birds are placed directly into, eliminating the need for a habituation period. Birds were removed after 10 min if they did not sit down. A clear negative correlation between time spent standing and gait score was observed and the mean LTL durations for birds with each gait score were all significantly different. 97.4% of birds sat within the 10-min limit. In this study, one observer was able to test 4 birds simultaneously, meaning that 12-15 birds could be tested per half an hour period. Groves and Muir (2014) further modified this test by reducing the maximum test duration to 5 min. In this study, birds were tested in groups of 30 using a tub containing 3 cm of water at 31-33 °C. Birds were not gait scored in this study.

Weimer et al. (2020) used two versions of a modified latency to lie test to assess leg health of broilers raised on either litter or wire flooring. Birds were allowed to settle in a dry storage tub before being placed either individually or in a group of five into a new container. 3 cm of tepid water (32°C) was then added, stimulating the birds to stand. The time stopped after a bird was sitting for 3 s, or the maximum test duration of 15 min was reached. All birds were tested both individually and in a group in a randomised order. The researchers hypothesised that birds raised on wire would have shorter latencies to lie, however they surprisingly did not find differences between the two rearing styles. Testing birds individually or in groups can have an impact on test results. For instance, testing in groups can influence behaviour and can cause birds to experience stress-induced self-analgesia or attentional shifts (Gentle, 2001). Birds tested individually are more likely to display pain-related behaviours than when they are tested in groups (Gentle and Corr, 1995). For this reason, Weimer et al. (2020) wanted to assess the impact of the LTL test conducted individually and in groups. The authors found that the LTL durations were generally lower for birds when tested in groups, however there was a large amount of variation, and the differences were not deemed statistically significant. Other researchers have further modified the LTL with water test using smaller groups of 5 or 6 birds, and a maximum test duration of 370 s (6.2 min) (Paz et al., 2019; Barbosa et al., 2022).

Santos et al. (2022) tested birds using both a group obstacle course and a LTL with water test. Their LTL test apparatus allowed for testing two birds simultaneously in a Plexiglas tank divided into two compartments with a plastic mesh partition. A wood cover was placed over top to prevent the birds from escaping. The authors recorded the latency before lying down for the first time which was defined as the breast touching the water for at least 5 s. Birds remained in the test pen for the entire 10-min duration of the test and thus the frequency of all lying events were also recorded. The authors found that slower-growing genotypes had longer latencies to lie than fast-growing genotypes. Previous studies have found associations with both the LTL and group obstacle tests with gait scores, however in this study, no correlation between the LTL test and group obstacle test variables were found, suggesting that these tests are assessing different aspects of mobility.

Singh et al. (2017) utilized an individual LTL test with 10 cm of water and a 10 min maximum test duration. The authors observed an unexpectedly large amount of variation in the LTL results. They speculated this may have been a result of changes in the temperature of the water, as testing was performed during the colder months of the year. Further, in this study the LTL test was performed after an obstacle course test which may have contributed to fatigue.

Latency to lie without water

In an attempt to simplify the LTL test and to limit stress associated with handling, a LTL test without the use of a tub or water was developed (Bailie et al., 2013; Bailie and O'Connell, 2014). The authors randomly selected 20-25 birds from within the house using a transparent grid marked with an 'x'. The bird lying closest to the 'x' when viewing the grid at arm's length was selected for scoring. The lying bird was then approached and encouraged to stand. Time until the bird sat back down was recorded using a stopwatch. The test was terminated after the bird sat or 5 min was reached. Baxter et al. (2021) employed a very similar test, but with a limit of 2 min.

Norring et al. (2019) also implemented the LTL test without water in an experimental facility. Two broilers from each pen (13-15 birds total per pen) were selected for scoring. Using a fence, the selected bird was separated from its pen-mates and allowed to sit down. Once the bird sat, it was gently encouraged to stand using a 1 m long blunt stick. The time until the bird sat back down was recorded. This test was repeated three times. After the LTL test, gait scoring using the Bristol scale was performed. Latencies obtained in this study were comparable to those obtained by Bailie et al. (2013), though both had considerably shorter latencies than those reported in studies that utilized a water bath. This is beneficial in terms of time required to conduct the test (most birds lied down within 30 s), though the association between the LTL test without water and Bristol gait scores remains unclear.

With advancements in technology, automated methods for capturing latencies to lie have been developed (Aydin et al., 2015; Aydin, 2017b). Aydin et al. (2015) placed broilers with known gait scores (Bristol scale) on one end of a 2.4 m runway with conspecifics at the opposite end. A top-down camera was used to record the test. An image-processing algorithm was applied to automatically detect the number of lying events and the latency to lie duration. The algorithm was able to correctly classify 83% of the lying events of the 250 broilers tested,

and gait score and lying events were found to be positively correlated. Latency to lie results were similar to those presented in Weeks et al. (2002), with lame birds (gait scores of 3 and 4) sitting down significantly earlier than non-lame birds. A strong negative correlation was also found between the LTL and gait scores.

More recently, Aydin (2017b) conducted a similar test utilizing a test corridor with an overhead 3D camera. Number of lying events and LTL were automatically detected over a 5-min test period. Using this setup, 93% of lying events were able to be correctly classified. A significant positive correlation was found between gait score and number of lying events, while a significant negative correlation was found between gait score and LTL. Benefits to these automated methods are that they can obtain estimates automatically and in real time. This technology also has the potential to be scaled up to be able to assess multiple chickens simultaneously. The 3D cameras, while more expensive than 2D cameras, have the advantage of being more robust in variable lighting conditions which are typical in commercial farm environments. This could explain the improved accuracy compared to the test using a 2D camera setup.

Summary

The latency to lie test provides an objective, continuous measure that appears to be highly correlated with gait scores. These methods do not require training and better allow for the comparison between different farms scored by different observers. While this test does require time to conduct, multiple birds may be scored simultaneously by the same observer, and in studies most birds sit down within 5 min (Weeks et al., 2002). This test may also be gentler on birds that are experiencing pain, as birds are not forced to walk. Birds that are severely lame may choose to remain lying when water is added, and thus will be removed from the test without having to bear weight on their limbs. Methods without the use of water show great potential for use under farm conditions, however more work is needed to assess the test's validity, reliability, and feasibility.

Rotarod test

In rodents, an established and standardized method to assess walking ability is the rotarod test. This consists of placing animals on a rotating rod that either gradually increases in velocity or remains rotating at a fixed speed. A maximum test duration is set, and the animal is placed back on the rod after falls. Variables such as latency to fall, total duration of time spent on the rod during a test session, and total number of falls are commonly measured. Malchow et al. (2019) aimed to evaluate the use of this method for assessing walking ability in broilers, with the hypothesis that poor walking ability may have a negative effect on balance, thus negatively impacting their ability to remain on the rotating rod. The rotarod test consisted of a 50 mm wooden rod covered in a thin layer of black rubber fixed to a mechanical system that controlled the rotational speed. The rotation of the rod was controlled automatically via software that increased the velocity every 1.545 s up until a maximum value of 2.1 rps was achieved. The rod was stopped after a bird actively or passively left the rod, or when the maximum time period of 5 min was reached. Gait scoring was carried out prior to the rotarod test using the Bristol scale. This study found that the latency to leave the rod was significantly associated with gait score, with birds with gait scores of 0 and 1 staying significantly longer on

the rotating rod compared to birds with scores of 2, 3, and 4. Overall this method allowed for the assessment of walking ability as a continuous measurement without the need for intense observer training. A downside to the test is the requirement for electricity and space to set up the equipment.

Kinetic and kinematic techniques

Kinematic approaches

Kinetic (walking forces) and kinematic (body motion) measures may also be used to quantitatively assess walking ability. In early studies, footprints have been used to perform a gait analysis. Birds' feet were dipped in ink before they were encouraged to walk across a 2 m long runway covered in white paper. The prints were scanned, and track width and step length were analysed using a program. Results showed that broilers with reduced weight had longer stride lengths. This has advanced to examining attributes of their stride, in addition to simply the step length and track width. Reiter and Bessei (1997) marked birds' bodies in three locations (cloacal region and both feet joints) with reflective markers and recorded birds from behind as they walked on a treadmill. Vertical and horizontal movements were recorded over time. The movement of laying hens and broilers with and without obvious leg disorders were compared. Results showed that vertical movements were comparable between all three groups of birds, however there were notable horizontal differences of the feet and the body centre oscillation. The authors concluded that the patterns and frequency of feet movements and body oscillations may be used to quantitatively describe gait abnormalities in broilers. A similar, more recent study has looked at utilising a commercially available system to collect 3D kinematic data using infrared cameras as birds walk along a 3m long runway (Caplen et al., 2012). Birds were fitted with saddles and leg bands with reflective markers and were gait scored using the Bristol method. It was found that birds with a gait score of 0 walked more quickly and had longer lengths and durations of their stride. Birds with a gait score of 3 took shorter, quicker strides and had greater back movement in both planes. In order to obtain quality results, the markers must be positioned to a fixed position on the bird which can be difficult as skin displacement is natural during movement.

Studies attempting to use velocity and acceleration to predict gait score have found that these relationships are not simple (Dawkins et al., 2009; Dawkins et al., 2012). Therefore, Nääs et al. (2018) applied paraconsistent logic to predict the gait scores of 25 birds as they walked down a runway and were video recorded from the side. This methodology was able to estimate gait scores 1, 2 and 3 with an accuracy of 50%, 70% and 100%, respectively. Pereira et al. (2021) also attempted to predict gait score (on a 6-point scale) using walking velocity. A novel automated method using an unrest index found that birds with gait scores of 4 and 5 had the lowest displacement rates. Similar to other studies, this study struggled to distinguish between birds with similar gait scores since birds with gait scores 0 and 1, 2 and 3, and 4 and 5 had very similar walking speeds.

Doornweerd et al. (2021) evaluated the performance of a pose-estimation network created using data from both broilers and turkeys. Video was collected of broilers walking along a corridor from behind. For training, eight keypoints were annotated in each frame: the head,

neck, and the left and right knees, hocks and feet. In testing, the multi-species model resulted in high error rates, however the within-species model provided much more accurate keypoint predictions from which aspects of gait motion could be obtained. Fodor et al. (2023) employed post-estimation to assess walking ability in broilers. Authors used a deep learning model to detect and track 8 keypoints on a bird from behind as they walked down a runway. Gait scoring was conducted using a 6-point scale which was similar to the Bristol scale. It was found that birds with poorer gait scores had sharper hock joint lateral angles and lower step height.

Other studies have examined key points on birds using a side view, using still images and 2D and 3D video. For instance, Mendes et al. (2023) used frontal and lateral photos to process and analyse geometric properties of broilers that had been gait scored using the Bristol scale. Positive correlations of gait score with the angles between the tibia and femur as well as between the medial malleolus and the centre of the foot were found, with wider angles being associated with greater gait scores. Naas et al. (2021) employed a machine learning approach to assess walking ability. Side-view video was captured of broilers as they walked across a 1 m long platform. Gait scores were assigned using a 6-point scale. The model was able to correctly classify 91% of the 200 broilers tested as either sound (gait score of 0) or lame (gait score of 1, 2, 3 or 4).

The possibility to detect poor walking ability from overhead cameras could potentially allow for cameras to be mounted from the ceiling on commercial farms, allowing for continuous monitoring of broiler walking ability. This could allow for remote, real-time observations of undisturbed birds. A few studies have developed methods to assess walking ability in test corridors using overhead cameras. Aydin et al. (2017a) used computer vision to detect feature variables including speed, step frequency, step length and lateral body oscillations. Positive correlations were found between all variables and gait score, and a significant relationship between step length and gait score was found. This algorithm, however, struggled to distinguish between lower gait scores (0, 1 and 2) due to these birds displaying similar feature variables. The authors suggested the inclusion of additional features such as foot curls or wing use to improve the ability to distinguish between birds with less severe walking impairments in future work.

Broiler moving trajectories and 16 metrics related to locomotion were obtained using top view images in a study by Li et al. (2023). Birds were gait scored using the 3-point scale developed by Webster et al. (2008). Using deep-learning algorithms, depth sensing and image processing, the model was able to track birds in a test corridor with 100% accuracy. Broilers with lower gait scores showed more obvious lateral body oscillation patterns and moved significantly faster than broilers with higher gait scores.

Nasiri et al. (2022) employed a deep convolutional neural network to detect and track seven key points on the body of broilers using a top down view in a broiler house. Birds were gait scored using the Bristol scale, and birds were found to have scores ranging from 0 to 3. This model was able to correctly classify 95% of the broilers assessed. Out of 40 birds tested, the model was able to correctly classify all but two birds, where a bird with a gait score of 0 (by human observer) was classified by the model as a 1, and a bird with a gait score of 3 being

classified as a 2. The average per-class accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity and area under the curve for the model were 97.5, 95, 95.54, 98.39 and 96.92, respectively.

Kinetic approaches

Measures of ground reaction forces as a bird walks may be associated with walking ability. For example, if putting body weight on limb is painful, or if a limb has muscular or skeletal abnormalities, a bird may bear less weight on that limb. These differences in forces between the limbs or within the foot can be detected using various types of force plates. Corr et al. (1998) used a system known as a pedobarograph (a type of force plate) built into a 2 m long runway which measured the pressure being applied by the toes and footpad while walking. Variables assessed included speed, cadence, step length, step width, step angle, and plantar pressure. Broilers were placed on one end of the runway and were stimulated to walk across the glass surface of the force plate by a person from behind, with the goal of having the bird walk in a relatively straight line at a constant speed. Data from 5 runs from each bird were collected. Results indicated that variation within birds was high, as well as variation between birds. This could hinder the ability to collect data that is representative of individual birds' "typical" gait pattern, as large samples sizes and number of runs would be required. It is possible that the speed of movement could have impacted the results, as could the glass surface which could have altered how the birds moved. Birds assessed in this study were clinically sound, however past work had demonstrated that stride length decreases and step width increases in lame broilers (Farage-Elawar, 1989; Corr et al., 2003a). Additionally, the position of the medial toe has been shown to be associated with walking ability, with sounds birds placing the toe pointing inwards, while in lame birds the toe is more aligned with the direction of walking (Sheets et al., 1987; Corr et al., 2003a). The amount of plantar pressure may also be used to assess walking ability by comparing pressure patterns between birds, between the feet of individual birds, and between different areas of the foot.

Corr et al. (2003b) aimed to characterise parameters representative of "normal" walking. Similar to their previous paper, high variability was observed in the measurements, decreasing the potential for this method to have practical applications, at least in its current form. Unfortunately, increasing sample size (number of crossings per individual across the pressure plate) did not seem to improve the accuracy. The authors concluded that much of the observed variation could be attributed to changes in speed as the bird walked. Multiple walks over the force plate could have also contributed to fatigue, which could account for additional variance in the values. The variable with the lowest variability observed in this study was the maximum vertical force, which has been shown in previous studies to be a potential indicator of lameness.

Walking speed is known to be slower in lame broilers, as it reduces peak vertical forces, and therefore stresses on the musculoskeletal system (Corr et al., 2007). Lameness therefore may be able to be assessed by examining the peak vertical forces while accounting for body weight. Past studies in other species have documented decreased vertical loading rate with lameness (Budsberg et al., 1988; Ghosh et al., 1993; Rumph et al., 1993). Peak vertical forces in fast-growing broilers examined in this study were within ranges previously reported, however they

had significantly larger mediolateral forces, suggesting that the conformation of modern birds may be a major contributing factor in their observed gait patterns.

Sandilands et al. (2011) aimed to determine the association between gait scores and force plate readings with leg health parameters collected post-mortem. Gait scoring was conducted using the Bristol scale. Afterwards, scores were binarised, with scores of 1 and 2 placed in one group, and scores greater than 3 in another group. No gait scores of 0 were observed. A force plate was embedded into a 1.6 m long enclosed walkway which was covered by a thin sheet of plywood to prevent slipping. The bird was placed on one end and allowed to walk across the platform to be reunited with their conspecifics. Each bird walked across the force plate once and several footprints were analysed. For each test, bodyweight, number of steps, average speed, total distance between each step and cadence were measured. For each footprint, data on 26 variables were collected including which foot (right or left), stance time, step length and width, step angle and various force measures. Force plate measures were significantly related with gait scores greater than 3 from 3 weeks of age, with fit improving up until 6 weeks of age. Factors of body weight and total distance between each step were most related to gait score. However, in general the variables from the force plate were poor predictors of gait score. Relationships between the force plate values and gait scores were more closely related to one another than to the presence of leg abnormalities identified during post-mortem analysis. To identify birds with leg abnormalities, the authors estimated that between 1440 and 8290 birds would need to be tested by either method (force plate or gait scores), assuming a prevalence of abnormalities of 20% and a power of 90%. Similar to previous studies, the authors believed that increasing the number of times each bird is tested could improve the accuracy of the force plate test.

An additional study aimed to assess locomotion by analysing peak vertical force on both feet while walking across a 1 m walkway with a thin mat lined with piezoelectric crystal sensors (Nääs et al., 2010). The authors concluded that asymmetric movement during locomotion could be captured using a force plate which measures vertical peak force in both feet, though associations with gait scores were not examined.

Summary

While use of a force plate is not practical on commercial farms, advancements in computer vision show some potential for detecting and analysing various key features which are linked with walking ability. With this technology, continuous, real-time predictions may be made on individual broilers without disturbing the flock. This also reduces the biosecurity risk that accompanies bringing human observers and equipment onto farms.

Measuring activity

Use of sensors and video for automated behavioural detection have the potential for being used to assess walking ability, both at a flock such as with the study of optical flow, or an individual level such as with wearable accelerometers. Use of these technologies could allow for the monitoring of walking ability throughout the entire lives of the broilers in a non-invasive manner. Dawkins et al. (2009) obtained optical flow data (mean, variance, skewness and kurtosis) using overhead cameras placed in ten commercial broiler houses. Within each flock, 50-100 birds were individually gait scored on a 3-point scale (Webster et al., 2008). All

four optical flow measures were significantly correlated with the percentage of birds within a house showing high gait scores. Manual decoding of focal animals was also performed, and negative correlations between high gait scores and time spent walking and number of strides per min were found. Dawkins et al. (2012) similarly found that the skew and kurtosis of optical flow patterns were correlated with poor walking ability, and these correlations were apparent in birds as young as 20 days old. Dawkins et al. (2013) hypothesized that a wider spread of gait scores may contribute to the observed skew and kurtosis in these studies due to the wider variety of movement compared to more uniform movement patterns observed in sound and health flocks.

A few publications have utilised the eYeNamic software from Fancom to automatically obtain activity data from groups of broilers using ceiling mounted cameras (Aydin et al., 2010; Silvera et al., 2017; Van Hertem et al., 2018). Aydin et al. (2010) employed this system to determine activity levels of broilers with various gait scores (ranging from 0 to 5 on the Bristol scale). Test pens containing five birds with the same gait score were video recorded and assessed for activity at the pen level. The authors found that the relationship between gait score and activity was not linear, with birds of a gait score of 3 being the most active, and birds with gait scores of 4 and 5 displaying significantly lower amounts of activity than birds with all other gait scores. In a second experiment where birds representing all gait scores were mixed into a single pen, spatial analysis revealed that birds with gait scores of 0 and 3 were found to explore the pen to a greater extent than birds with a gait score of 4, suggesting that spatial use is correlated with activity metrics (Aydin et al., 2013).

Silvera et al. (2017) obtained automated activity recordings using the eYeNamic system in 5 commercial broiler flocks. A sample of 100-200 birds per flock were gait scored using the 6-point Bristol scale. The house was recorded using a single overhead camera while an assessor performed a transect walk through the house. The activity index could range from 0 (no activity) up to 100 (all birds moved). Authors found that the birds' direct response to a human (peak activity relative to baseline activity) was significantly related to their walking ability, though care should be taken when using this metric as bird fearfulness could impact the results. No significant relationship was found between birds' baseline activity (activity when there was no human present) and gait scores. Van Hertem et al. (2018) also used the eYeNamic software to generate an activity index and distribution index of broilers housed across five different commercial farms. This study differed from Silvera et al. (2017) in that a transect walk was not performed to stimulate the birds. Gait score was conducted using the Bristol scale on a sample of at least 100 birds per farm. Contrary to past studies, authors observed a negative correlation between activity level and average gait score of the flock and a positive correlation between flock distribution index and gait score, meaning that flocks with higher gait scores were more evenly distributed.

Bayesian modelling of optical flow data has been employed to predict gait scores in commercial settings (Roberts et al., 2012). A model based on daily mean, variance, skew and kurtosis of optical flow data was able to predict gait score by as early as 13 days of age, about a week earlier than the model developed by Dawkins et al. (2012) could, even though gait

scoring using the Bristol scale was not conducted until day 28. This method could in theory be used to warn producers early on of deteriorating walking abilities.

Yang et al. (2023) explored the potential of modelling gait score using activity and distribution indexes obtained automatically using cameras and the eYeNamic system as well as body weight obtained from automatic weighing systems. Broilers were housed in pens in groups of 12 and were gait scored using the 6-point scale modified by Garner et al. (2002). This study found that the activity index was effective as an indicator of gait, with a negative correlation being observed. Body weight obtained with the automatic weighing system was also highly correlated with average gait score. The distribution index, however, was not significantly related to gait.

The major downside to methods using optical flow data is that they can only provide information at the flock level. As welfare is an individual experience, data at the level of the individual is optimal. Van der Sluis et al. (2021) employed an ultra-wideband tracking system to obtain walking ability data on individual broilers housed in a group setting. Birds were fitted with backpacks containing sensors and were gait scored using a 6-point system similar to the Bristol scale. Birds were then classified as having a “good gait” (scores 0-2) or a “suboptimal gait” (scores 3-5). Results indicated that there was a relationship between gait scores and various measures of activity, with birds with “suboptimal” gaits having lower activity levels. However, the gait score explained relatively little of the variation in activity levels, with factors such as age, weight and genotype accounting for greater proportions of variance.

An alternative method for obtaining activity data at an individual level are body worn accelerometers. These sensors are relatively small and lightweight and allow for continuous monitoring of broiler activity level that could be utilised to make inferences about their gait score. Pearce et al. (2023) attached accelerometers to the backs of broiler chickens to explore the link between percentage of time spent active and gait scores obtained using a 6-point scale, however no significant relationship was observed. Past studies that did find a negative association between gait score and activity utilised birds with all gait scores, including those with scores of 4 and 5, while this study only included birds with scores from 0-3. In this study and others, activity decreased linearly from scores 0 to 2, but increase in birds with scores of 3. The reason for this counter intuitive increase is unknown, but if this pattern is consistent then there may be potential in using activity data to predict gait scores. Future research is needed to explore specific movement patterns along the X, Y and Z axis to potentially identify more subtle changes in gait. While accelerometers offer the potential of continuous individual monitoring, it is currently impractical for use due to the cost, labour required and the possibly impacts they may have on broiler behaviour.

Conclusions

Currently, gait scoring remains the most commonly used method for assessing the walking ability of broilers on farm, despite its inherent subjectivity and required training. This is likely to the ease of conducting the scoring, as it can be completed during a transect walk during an inspection. It also requires very little to no equipment, depending on whether a pen is used to capture groups of birds.

The latency to lie test, especially when conducted without water, appears to be the most feasible objective scoring system available for use during on farm inspections. This test does not require any training and can be conducted in a timely manner if multiple birds are assessed simultaneously. However, this test currently lacks sufficient validation.

Other forms of assessment such as the rotarod test, obstacle courses and force plates are not practical for use on farm due to the required equipment. Computer vision approaches do show some potential for automating walking ability assessment, however many of these methods fail to be able to distinguish between distinct gait scores, especially between scores of 0, 1 and 2. Accelerometers also have potential for use in experimental settings or at breeding facilities, however they are likely too costly and require too much handling to be practical for use during inspections and they require additional validation. A summary of the positives and limitations of the reviewed methods is available in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the major positives and limitations of the reviewed available methods for assessing walking ability in broilers. Validity, reliability, and feasibility estimates are also provided (low (+), moderate (++) , high (+++), unknown (?)).

Method	Positives	Limitations	Validity	Reliability	Feasibility
Gait scoring	Low time requirement, does not require equipment (a pen is optional), validated method, 6-point scales allow for wide range of severity	Requires extensive training, can have low reliability, difficulty directly comparing scores from different observers, ideally should have 2 observers with different viewpoints, encouraging birds to walk can bias results	+++	+	+++
Obstacle courses	Objective, can be conducted on groups in the home pen	Not practical for use on farm, requires video recording and decoding, relies on the birds being motivated to reach the other side, require habituation, time consuming	+++	++	+
Latency to lie	Objective, does not require training, time effective, can be easily implemented on farm, shows strong link with Bristol gait score, measures are continuous, does not require forcing lame birds to walk, method with water is validated	Method with water requires a container and a way to maintain water temperature, method without water requires validation	? (without water), +++ (with water)	+++	+++ (without water), ++ (with water)
Rotarod test	Objective, highly linked with gait scores	Not practical for use on farm, requires specific equipment and a computer set up	++	+++	+
Kinetic and kinematic techniques	Can be non-invasive, computer vision methods can allow for continuous monitoring across entire lifespan, cameras pose low biosecurity risk	Current available methods struggle to distinguish between low gait scores, requires more development and validation before it could be considered to replace manual gait scoring	+	++	+
Activity	Objective, can provide either flock or individual level data, cameras are a low	Optical flow methods only provide flock level data, accelerometers are not	+	++	+

	biosecurity risk, can provide continuous non-invasive monitoring across the life of the flock	practical for commercial farm use, more development is necessary before it can replace manual gait scoring			
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Appendix

Table A1: Bristol Gait scoring criteria from Kestin et al. (1992).

Score	Criteria
0	The bird walked normally with no detectable abnormality; it was dexterous and agile. Typically the foot was picked up and put down smoothly and each foot was brought under the bird's centre of gravity as it walked (rather than the bird swaying). Often, the toes were partially furled while the foot was in the air. The bird should have been capable of balancing on one leg and walking backwards easily if necessary. It should also have been in full command of where it was going, and been able to deviate its course easily to avoid other birds.
1	The bird had a slight defect which was difficult to define precisely but would have precluded its use for breeding if gait had been the sole selection criterion at the standard of a pedigree breeder. For example, the bird may have taken unduly large strides which, although the observer may not have recognized the exact cause, produced an uneven gait.
2	The bird had a definite and identifiable defect in its gait but the lesion did not hinder it from moving or competing for resources. For example, it may have been sufficiently lame on one leg to produce a rolling gait which did not seriously compromise its manoeuvrability, acceleration or speed.
3	The bird had an obvious gait defect which affected its ability to move about. For example, the defect could take the form of a limp, jerky or unsteady strut, or severe splaying of one leg as it moved. The bird often preferred to squat when not coerced to move, and its manoeuvrability, acceleration and speed were affected.
4	The bird had a severe gait defect. It was still capable of walking, but only with difficulty and when driven or strongly motivated. Otherwise it squatted down at the first available opportunity. Its acceleration, manoeuvrability and speed were all severely affected.
5	The bird was incapable of sustained walking on its feet. Although it may have been able to stand, locomotion could only be achieved with the assistance of the wings or by crawling on the shanks.

Table A2: Gait scoring system used by the Welfare Quality assessment protocol (Welfare Quality®, 2009).

Score	Criteria
0	Normal, dexterous and agile
1	Slight abnormality, but difficult to define
2	Definite and identifiable abnormality
3	Obvious abnormality, affects ability to move
4	Severe abnormality, only takes a few steps
5	Incapable of walking

Table A3: Gait scoring system used by the RSPCA (RSPCA, 2017).

Score	Criteria
0	The bird displays smooth, fluid locomotion. Typically the foot is picked up and put down smoothly and each foot is brought under the bird's centre of gravity as it walks (rather than the bird swaying). Often, the toes are partially curled while the foot is in the air.
1	The bird has a slight defect in its gait that is difficult to define precisely. The bird may take unduly large strides, be unsteady or wobble when it walks, which produces an uneven gait, but the problem leg is unclear/cannot be easily identified.
2	The bird has a definite and identifiable gait abnormality, but this does not affect its ability to move. The bird may make short, quick, unsteady steps with one leg, but is not sufficiently lame to seriously compromise its ability to move, i.e. manoeuvre, accelerate and run.
3	The bird has an obvious gait defect that affects its ability to move. The bird may have a limp, jerky or unsteady strut, or splay one leg as it moves. The bird often prefers to squat when not coerced to move, and will not run.
4	The bird has a severe gait defect. The bird is capable of walking, but only with difficulty and when driven or strongly motivated. Otherwise it squats down at the first available opportunity.
5	The bird is incapable of sustained walking on its feet. Although it may be able to stand, the bird cannot walk except with the assistance of the wings or by crawling on the shanks.

Table A4: Modified gait scoring system developed by Garner et al. (2002).

Score	Criteria
0	Smooth, fluid locomotion. The foot is furred while raised.
1	The bird is unsteady, or wobbles when it walks. However, the problem leg is unclear, or cannot be identified in the first 20 s of observation. The bird readily runs from the observer in the pen. The foot may remain flat when raised, but the rest of the stride is fluid and appears unimpaired.
2	The leg producing the gait defect can be identified within 20 s of observation. If a problem leg is identified after 20 s of observed locomotor behaviour then the bird is classed as gait score 1. However, the defect seems to have only a minor impact on biological function. Thus the bird will run from the observer spontaneously or if touched or nudged with a padded stick. If the bird does not run at full speed, it runs, walks or remains standing for at least 15 s after the observer in the pen has ceased to move towards or nudge it. Birds in this, and previous, scores are often observed to scratch their face with their feet - again indicating little impact on function. (The most common abnormality in this score is for the bird to make short, quick, unsteady steps with one leg, where the foot remains flat during the step.)
3	Although the bird will move away from the observer when approached or touched, or nudged, it will not run, and squats within 15 s or less of the observer in the pen ceasing to approach or nudge it. If the bird squats after 15 s have elapsed it is classified as gait score 2.
4	The bird remains squatting when approached or nudged. This criterion is assessed by approaching the bird, and if it remains squatting, gently nudging or touching the animal for 5 s. Animals may appear to rise but still be resting upon their hocks. Only rising to stand on

	both feet within 5 s of handling is counted - a birds which takes longer than 5 s to rise, or which does not rise at all is scored as 4, while a bird that rises in 5 s or else is counted as a 3 (or lower if gait is good). Nevertheless, the bird can walk when picked up by the observer and placed in a standing position, but quats immediately following one or two steps. (Squatting often involves a characteristic ungainly backwards fall.)
5	The bird cannot walk, and instead may shuffle along on its hocks. It may attempt to stand when approached but is unable to do so, and when placed on its feet is unable to complete a step with one or both legs.

Table A5: 3-point scoring system developed by Dawkins et al. (2004).

Score	Criteria
0	Bird walks with ease, has regular and even strides and is well balanced
1	Bird walks with irregular and uneven strides and appears unbalanced
2	Bird is reluctant to move and is unable to walk many strides before sitting down

Table A6: Scoring system developed by the National Chicken Council for audits within the US (Webster et al., 2008; National Chicken Council, 2022).

Score	Criteria
0	Bird can walk at least 5 feet with a balanced gait. Bird may appear ungainly but with no visible signs of lameness.
1	Bird can walk at least 5 feet, but appears awkward, uneven in steps.
2	Bird cannot walk 5 feet or there is obvious lameness. May shuffle on shanks or hocks with assistance of wings.

Table A7: 4-point scoring system developed by Yalçin et al. (1998).

Score	Criteria
0	The bird walked normally with no detectable abnormality
1	The bird was able to walk but had an obvious gait defect
2	The bird had a severe gait defect and walked only when driven
3	The bird did not walk